

HYDRIDES OF COBALT

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Hydrides of cobalt (mono and di) have been prepared according to the method described previously (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1943, 20, 213), and their properties studied. Dissociation pressures of the hydrides at different temperatures have been measured and their heats of formation calculated from the dissociation pressures. The apparatus previously described has been improved upon and data on dissociation pressures of nickel hydrides redetermined.

In a previous paper (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1943, 20, 213) the preparation and properties of the hydrides of nickel have been described. Following exactly the same procedure the hydrides of cobalt have been prepared. The reaction takes place according to the equation,

The apparatus used for preparation of this hydride in large quantities was almost the same as that used for nickel hydride (*loc. cit.*). Perfectly anhydrous and finely powdered cobalt chloride was added to dry ether in a wide-mouthed flask provided with a rubber bung through which passed a mercury-sealed glass stirrer, a dropping funnel and inlet and outlet tubes for hydrogen. A stream of hydrogen from the Kipp's apparatus, purified by passing through a mixture of potassium dichromate and conc. sulphuric acid, over red hot copper and finally through conc. sulphuric acid, was passed through the flask. When all the air had been displaced, a solution of freshly prepared PhMgBr in dry ether was run in. The phenyl magnesium bromide was freshly prepared otherwise the reaction did not take place satisfactorily. For every gram of cobalt chloride, 100 c.c. of dry ether were put into the flask and 50 c.c. of ethereal solution of PhMgBr containing 0.1 mol. of magnesium were used for the reaction. As soon as PhMgBr was introduced the colour of the suspension began to change and finally it became dark grey. The reaction took about 9 hours to complete.

Contrary to Balandin, Erofeev, Pecherskaya and Stakhanova's (*J. Gen. Chem. U. S. S. R.*; 1941, 11, 577; *Acta Physicochim. U.S.S.R.*, 1943, 18, 157; 1943, 18, 300) assumption that the metal is first precipitated in the colloidal form which absorbs hydrogen producing different hydrides, it was found that only one hydride is formed, although the preparations were carried out at 0°, 15° and 25° and in some cases the hydrogen was passed for longer periods even after the completion of the reaction. When the experiment was over, the composition of the substance was determined in the following manner. As the hydride was quantitatively decomposed by water or alcohol, a small quantity of the substance was taken out, introduced into a small flask, fitted with a dropping funnel and a delivery tube, which was connected to a Hempel's burette. A measured volume of dilute alcohol was added and the gas evolved was collected and measured. The volume of the hydrogen evolved by the hydride was obtained by subtracting the volume of the liquid introduced from

the total volume of the gas collected. The cobalt precipitated was dissolved in dilute sulphuric acid and precipitated by α -nitroso- β -naphthol. The precipitate was ignited and the cobalt estimated as CoSO_4 and also by dissolving the ignited residue in acid and estimating cobalt electrolytically. A large number of preparations was made at each temperature and the product obtained in each case was analysed and the results agreed quite closely. One typical series of results is recorded below.

TABLE I

Temp. of prepn.	Time of passing H_2 .	Wt. of Co.	Vol. of H_2 (N. T. P.)	Ratio Co/H.	Composition.
0°	8 hrs.	0.8885 g.	154.0 c.c.	1:2.09	CoH_2
0°	12	0.2738	100.5	1:1.96	..
15°	9	0.3730	147.8	1:2.11	..
15°	15	0.2334	91.5	1:2.05	..
25°	10	0.3067	120.0	1:2.08	..
25°	20	0.3835	150.0	1:2.07	..

The dissociation pressures of the hydride were determined at different temperatures. The hydride was repeatedly washed with ether to remove the organic matter and the magnesium salts present. It was then dried by putting it in a test tube at 25° and passing a stream of dry hydrogen through it. The substance thus obtained was perfectly dry and fairly pure though it still contained traces of magnesium salts as impurities.

For the purpose of measurement of dissociation pressure an all-glass apparatus as shown in Fig. 1 was used. It consisted of a long, closed-limb mercury manometer M connected with a bulb B

FIG. 1

which contained the substance and a tap T through which the apparatus was evacuated by means of a Töpler pump. The apparatus was then put inside an electrically maintained air thermostat which could be kept constant to $\pm 0.2^\circ$. The thermostat was set at definite temperatures and at each temperature it was kept for sufficiently long time until equilibrium was attained. At each temperature the heights of mercury in the two arms of the manometer were read off by means of a cathetometer provided with a vertical scale and a vernier. After the equilibrium had been established at a particular temperature and the readings had been taken, the apparatus was connected to the pump again and slightly evacuated to disturb the equilibrium. On keeping the apparatus at that temperature the original pressure was regained. This operation was carried out at every point

of observation. It was observed that up to 44° the pressure recorded in the first instance was reproducible even when the equilibrium was disturbed showing that the hydride is stable up to that temperature. At 45.8° , however, on disturbing the equilibrium after the first observation the pressure did not come back to the original value, but gave a lower value showing definitely that a new phase had appeared having a lower dissociation pressure than the first one. The region between 44° and 45.8° , indicated by the dotted line in Fig. 2, could not be explored with greater precision owing to experimental difficulties. Hence it can only be said that the transition lies somewhere between 44° and 45.8° . The temperature of the thermostat was further raised gradually up to 100° and the readings of pressure taken at different temperatures. The values were found to be reproducible and no other break was noticed. The composition of second solid phase at various temperatures above 50° was determined by analysis. It always corresponded to the formula CoH. One typical result for each temperature is tabulated below.

TABLE II

Temp. of bath.	Wt. of Co.	Vol. of H_2 (N. T. P.)	Ratio Co/H	Composition.
50°	0.1744 g.	30.5 c.c.	1:0.94	CoH
90	0.2300	41.1	1:0.95	"
130	0.2020	40.7	1:1.05	"
150	0.2737	50.2	1:0.98	"

It is evident from the table above that CoH is stable up to 150° . The dissociation pressure of the monohydride was measured from room temperature to 90° in the manner described for the dihydride. Several sets of measurements were carried out. The graphs plotted were almost identical. The mean values of the dissociation pressure at particular temperatures are recorded below.

TABLE III
Compound: CoH_2

Temp.	Press.	$1/T$ (abs.)	$\log_{10} p$
80.0°	4.02 cm.	0.003300	0.6042
32.5	4.70	0.003274	0.6721
35.0	5.80	0.003247	0.7243
37.9	6.00	0.003217	0.7782
40.8	6.90	0.003187	0.8388
44.0	7.80	0.003155	0.8921

TABLE IV
Compound: CoH

Temp.	Press.	$1/T$ (abs.)	$\log_{10} p$
29.8°	1.85 cm.	0.003302	0.2672
35.0	2.95	0.003247	0.4698
40.8	4.30	0.003192	0.6885
45.8	6.55	0.003187	0.8163
50.2	8.35	0.003094	0.9217
55.4	10.50	0.003045	1.0212
66.4	14.50	0.002946	1.1614
79.9	19.67	—	—
90.0	23.50	—	—

The results are represented graphically in Fig. 2 in which the upper curve is for CoH_2 which decomposes completely into CoH at a temperature somewhere between 44° and 45.8° . The unexplored region is indicated by the dotted line. The lower curve is for CoH . The transition from CoH_2 to CoH takes place in the region indicated by the dotted line.

The reactions $2\text{CoH}_2 \rightleftharpoons 2\text{CoH} + \text{H}_2$ and $2\text{CoH} \rightleftharpoons 2\text{Co} + \text{H}_2$ are reversible reactions but the dissociation of CoH_2 to CoH and H , with increasing temperature takes only a few hours to reach the equilibrium for a particular temperature. The rate of recombination of CoH and H to CoH_2 , however, is extremely slow. Similar is the case for the second reaction.

FIG. 2.

FIG. 3.

Curves 1—4 refer respectively to NiH , CoH , CoH_2 and NiH_2 .

The density of the dihydride was determined with respect to ether and was found to have a value of 0.533 at 30° .

The cobalt dihydride is a dark grey, almost black substance. It is fairly stable when kept under ether at temperatures below 5° . When purified and dried it has a crystalline appearance. It decomposes rapidly in contact with moist air but in dry air the rate of decomposition is slow at the ordinary temperature. It is decomposed quantitatively by water, alcohol or dilute acids, with the first two the decomposition is catalytic in nature resulting in the separation of metallic cobalt and only two atoms of hydrogen are evolved per molecule of the hydride, but with acids the cobalt salt of the acid is formed and four molecules of hydrogen are evolved per molecule of the hydride. The formation of the cobalt dihydride takes place in the same manner as suggested by Weichselfelder (*loc. cit.*) for the nickel hydride and in this case also traces of diphenyl etc. are produced as impurities. The properties of the monohydride are similar to dihydride. It is more stable than the dihydride. It has grey colour and crystalline appearance.

As discussed in the previous paper the heat of formation of CoH_2 and CoH was calculated by means of the Clapeyron-Clausius equation :

$$\frac{d \ln p}{dT} = \frac{Q}{RT^2}$$

which on integration gives :

$$Q = R \cdot \frac{\ln \frac{p_2}{p_1}}{\left(\frac{1}{T_2} - \frac{1}{T_1}\right)}$$

FIG. 4.

In Fig. 3 $\log_{10} p$ is plotted against $(1/T)10^3$ from which the values of the heat of formation of the two hydrides were calculated with reference to several points on the two straight lines and the mean values of the heat of formation over a range of temperature between 30° and 44° in the case of CoH_2 and from the room temperature to 90° in the case of CoH is given below :

$$\text{CoH}_2 = 9,400 \text{ cal}$$

$$\text{CoH} = 12,580 \text{ cal.}$$

The values of the heats of formation indicate that the monohydride is much more stable than the dihydride. This implies that the monohydride does not constitute a primary or an intermediate stage in the formation of the dihydride, and thus furnishes an indirect evidence that hydrogen does not react with the colloidal metal as suggested by the Russian workers.

After the paper on the nickel hydrides (*loc. cit.*) had been published it was found that the dissociation pressure data, obtained for the nickel hydrides by the apparatus given therein, was subject to many corrections and some errors had inadvertently crept up in the calorimeter hence the dissociation pressures of the nickel hydrides were again measured by the help of the new apparatus described

above and the mean of several sets of data obtained are given below in Tables V and VI. The observations were repeated many times and the graphs plotted in each case were found to be identical.

TABLE V
Compound: NiH₂.

Temp.	Press.	1/T (abs.)	log ₁₀ p.
31.0°	4.97 cm.	0.003289	0.6964
32.6	5.30	0.003273	0.7243
37.2	6.83	0.003224	0.7993
42.7	8.05	0.003168	0.9058
47.8	9.40	0.003118	0.9731
50.3	10.10	0.003093	1.0043
54.8	11.50	0.003050	1.0667

TABLE VI
Compound: NiH

Temp.	Press.	1/T (abs.)	log ₁₀ p.
33.2°	3.23 cm.	0.003266	0.5092
38.4	4.15	0.003211	0.6180
46.9	5.75	0.003126	0.7597
54.0	8.05	0.003058	0.9058
56.0	8.70	0.003040	0.9395
60.0	10.30	0.003030	1.0128
64.2	12.17	0.002965	1.0853
71.3	16.40	0.002904	1.2148
75.5	19.20	0.002870	1.2833
82.6	22.60	0.002812	1.3541
90.2	26.60	0.002758	1.4249
98.9	31.80	—	—

The results tabulated above are represented graphically in Fig. 4. The upper curve is for NiH₂ and the lower curve is for NiH. The transition takes place somewhere between 54.8° and 56° as indicated by the dotted line. The reactions noted below have also been found to be reversible but the rate of dissociation is much quicker compared to the rate of recombination.

The density of the dihydride of nickel has been determined with respect to ether and has a value of 0.508 at 31°.

The heats of formation of the two nickel hydrides have been recalculated from the new data represented graphically in Fig. 3, in which log₁₀p is plotted against (1/T)10³ and the mean value over a range of temperature from 33° to the transition temperature in the case of NiH₂ and up to about 100° in the case of NiH is given below:

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